

Fitting of data: JBW-NP-P-V4 2021-02-18_09-13-27
 $0.0188 \leq q \text{ (nm}^{-1}\text{)} \leq 25$
 Active parameters: 1, ranges: 1
 Background level: 0.129 ± 0.00176
 (Scaling factor: $3.1\text{e}+33 \pm 2.59\text{e}+31$)
 Timing: 10 repetitions of 56.9 ± 3.51 seconds

Range $1.500\text{e}-10$ to $1.500\text{e}-07$, vol-weighted
 totalValue: $2.188\text{e}-04 \pm 5.834\text{e}-07$
 mean: $3.372\text{e}-09 \pm 5.899\text{e}-12$
 variance: $6.887\text{e}-19 \pm 4.458\text{e}-20$
 skew: $1.958\text{e}+00 \pm 4.706\text{e}-01$
 kurtosis: $1.862\text{e}+01 \pm 4.098\text{e}+00$

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Measured vs. Fitted I

Sphere radius

Sphere radius

